

EFFECTS OF MOISTURE ON SELF-LUMINOUS GFRPS

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents an experimental study on self-luminous GFRPs' tensile and luminance properties under varying luminous powder concentrations and durations of water submersion. The experimental results indicate additional powder increased the material's afterglow properties to an extent, decreased its tensile strength at high concentrations, and improved its elastic modulus. Moisture weakened GFRP's tensile strength while the luminance properties remained virtually unaffected.

KEYWORDS

Self-luminance; Durability; Moisture; Tensile properties; Afterglow

INTRODUCTION

As the world is searching for more environmentally friendly ways to generate energy, self-luminous glass fiber reinforced polymers (GFRPs) are emerging as an alternative way of producing light. As luminous powder's brightness and time of emittance are increasing, self-luminous GFRPs can replace energy consuming light bulbs by providing street lighting when mounted to building façades (Kostic and Djokic, 2009), or to aesthetically illuminate buildings, bridges, and artwork at night.

GFRPs consist of glass fibers stiffened by a resin material, called the matrix, and can become self-luminous by mixing light conversion agents into the matrix. These light conversion agents are energy-storing materials that collect energy from surrounding light, such as the sun, and release this energy by illuminating immediately upon light source removal (Zhu et al., 2016). By adding this light conversion agent into a glass fiber reinforced polymer, the material can transform the surrounding light into energy that can then produce its own light. This photo luminescent phenomenon occurs immediately in the presence of light, but prolonged exposure leads to longer, brighter, and more colorful emittance (Chiatti et al., 2021). The lightness of light convergent agents experiences logarithmic decay as soon as the solar radiation is removed (Chiatti et al., 2021; Bai et al., 2015).

Bai et al. (2015) found the addition of luminous powder into a GFRP's matrix has negligible effect on the material's short-term load displacement response, failure mode, ultimate strength, and ultimate strain. Luminous powder's particle size is larger than the thickness of one glass fiber strand (Wang et al., 2020), so the powder is unable to embed into the fibers. The fibers are therefore virtually undisturbed, allowing their full tensile properties to be developed.

GFRP's mechanical properties vary depending on their environment. Glass fibers are hydrophobic while the matrix absorbs moisture through diffusion, the fiber-matrix interface capillarity effect, and voids and microcracks along the surface (Bian et al., 2012). Diffusion of water into the matrix has an adverse effect on a GFRP's tensile strength by causing hydrolysis to the resin and loosening the fiber-matrix bond (Bian et al., 2012; Wang et al., 2015a; Wang et al., 2015b; Al-Salloum et al., 2012). A study conducted by Al-Salloum et al. (2012) found GFRP bars immersed in ambient tap water for 6, 12, and 18 months experienced a decrease in tensile strength of approximately 2.7%, 1.8%, and 5.4%, respectively.

Although the durability of regular GFRPs in moist environment have been extensively studied, its effects on self-luminous GFRPs are unknown. To assess the durability of self-luminous GFRPs during outdoor application, this study aims to evaluate the effects of moisture and varying luminous powder

concentration on the material's tensile strength and afterglow performance. In this study, GFRP's failure mode, tensile strength, ultimate strain, modulus of elasticity, and brightness were examined with varying luminance concentrations and durations of water submersion.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The specimens were created using rubber mold method. In this method, epoxy was poured into rubber cut-outs and glass fiber strands were then pressed into the epoxy before the specimens were left to dry. The rubber mold allows for easy specimen extraction and consistent sizes after hardening. The size of each specimen in this study followed the ASTM D-3039 recommendation for 0° unidirectional FRPs to be 250 mm × 15 mm. The mold used was 3 mm thick to accommodate the fiber mat and was made by pouring a silicone mixture over top of five 250 mm × 15 mm × 3 mm metal bars in a box. The same metal bars were used as a template to cut glass fiber strands to the appropriate size.

To create the GFRP's matrix, the epoxy primer and saturant were poured into the beaker in a 2:1 volume ratio per the manufacturer's instructions. If needed, industrial green glow powder was then added to the beaker as a percentage of the epoxy's weight. In this study, the luminous powder in the specimens ranged from 0% to 80% of the epoxy weight with increments of 20%. The primer, saturant, and luminous powder were then mixed with a stirring rod for five minutes and placed in a vacuum for 5 minutes to eliminate air. A layer of the epoxy solution was poured into the mold, followed by one glass fiber strip pressed into the mold, and topped off with more epoxy solution. The stirring rod was then rolled over top to flatten the specimens, clear excess epoxy, and release any air voids. The specimens then air dried for 24 hours in ambient temperature before extrusion and trimming of excess epoxy.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Test Procedure

The self-luminous GFRP specimens were tested for light emittance over time. To do so, a specimen was placed in the middle of a closed studio box where LED light strips, attached to the top of the box, were turned on for 5 minutes to activate the specimen. After 5 minutes, a light meter was slid overtop of the specimen before turning the LED lights off. The sensor sat on a 3.8 cm tall chair to maintain equivalent height above specimens for all tests (Figure 1). The specimen's luminance, measured in lux, was then recorded over time until the light meter, with a precision of 0.01 lx, could no longer detect light.

Figure 1: Light meter recording the luminance of a specimen

Luminance in Control Condition

Initially, an activation study was conducted to determine the amount of time needed to completely "activate" each specimen to their maximum luminance. The luminance test with a varying activation time of 5, 7.5, and 10 minutes was conducted on three specimens with luminous powder equaling 20%, 40%, 60% and 80% of the epoxy weight. From this study, the light activation between 5 and 10 minutes displayed negligible difference in luminance over time, so a 5-minute activation time was adopted for the remaining tests.

After the 5-minute activation time was adopted, the luminance test was then conducted on five specimens for each % epoxy weight of luminance powder to study the effect of powder concentration on light output. To allow the light meter to adjust to the removal of activation light, the first luminance reading was observed after 15 seconds. Although the meter did not register light less than 0.01 lx, the specimen was still visibly glowing at the end of each test. Figure 2 shows the comparison between a specimen at the start and end of a test.

(a) At the start of a test (b) At the end of a test

Figure 2: Light emittance of a specimen

In the control condition, the addition of luminous powder significantly improved the material's brightness and time of immittance. The rate at which the luminance and duration increased, however, became less gradual as the powder concentration increased, shown graphically in Figure 3. The GFRP experienced a significant increase in light intensity from 20% wt. to 40% wt., while a gradual increase occurred between 60% wt. and 80% wt. Based off the values provided in the table, the initial luminance increased about 108% and the duration increased about 78% between the 20% and 40% epoxy weight. The initial luminance and duration from 60% to 80% epoxy weight increased only about 4% and 18%, respectively. Therefore, adding luminous powder beyond 80% of the epoxy weight will not significantly enhance a GFRP's light output or duration.

Figure 3: Averaged luminance over time for control condition

TENSILE TEST

Test Procedure

After the luminance tests, the specimens were subjected to a quasi-static tensile test as defined by ASTM D-3039 (Figure 4). The specimen's width and thickness were measured with a caliper and averaged from three measurements at separate locations near its center. Each specimen was then placed into a 20-kip hydraulic actuator and loaded at a strain rate of 2 mm/min until failure. An extensometer was fastened along the length of each sample to record the strain of the material during testing, where three data samples were collected every second. The extensometer's teeth sat on a

small piece of athletic tape wrapped around the specimen's surface to reduce slip caused by cracking. If failure occurred within or at the edge of the grips, the tensile strength and ultimate strain results were considered invalid. However, the modulus of elasticity was still determined from the initial portion of the stress vs. strain curve. From each test, the load acting on the GFRP, the corresponding strain it experienced, and the failure type and location were recorded.

Figure 4: Tensile test setup

Tensile Properties in Control Condition

When GFRP fracture occurs, there are three different failure types for GFRPs: type I is brittle failure, type II is brittle failure with fiber pullout, and type III is brittle failure with debonding and/or matrix failure (Agarwal et al., 2017). In this study, roughly 15% of specimens exhibited Type II failure and 85% exhibited Type III failure in control specimens.

The specimens displayed similar failure modes regardless of if luminous powder existed in the matrix or not. The amount of luminous powder added to the matrix did not significantly affect the GFRP's tensile strength until 60% epoxy weight or more powder was added to the matrix. The average tensile strengths of the specimens with 0, 20% and 40% luminance were 167 Mpa, 171 Mpa, and 170 Mpa, respectively, while the strengths of the 60% and 80% luminance specimens were 138.6 MPa and 158.2 MPa, respectively. The tensile strength vs. luminous powder concentration chart is shown with an error bar indicating the data range in Figure 5a. At around 60% luminance, there was likely too much glow powder in the matrix, hindering the epoxy to fully bond to the fibers and causing a reduction in strength. Surprisingly, the 80% epoxy wt. specimens' tensile strength was almost 20 MPa higher than that of the 60% epoxy wt. This was likely due to various levels of luminous powder clustering within the matrix. Mixing the luminous powder with epoxy and pouring it into the molds was a variable process. Small clusters of powder could still exist after mixing the epoxy or it could be more concentrated in a certain area of the specimen after the matrix was poured in the mold. These small clusters or higher powder concentrations could have blocked the epoxy from properly bonding to the fibers, creating a weak point in the specimen. As more luminous powder was used, the possibility of clusters blocking the fiber to matrix bond could increase, but since mixing the powder and epoxy together creates a random distribution of powder, it is possible that the 60% specimens had either larger clusters or concentrations of luminous powder in the material.

The results indicate that the ultimate strain remained unaffected with the addition of luminous powder. As shown in Figure 5b, the average ultimate strain was consistent among specimen types, except for the 60% luminance specimens. The 60% specimens seem to be an outlier since they had a much lower ultimate strain than the 40% and 80% luminance specimens. This provides more evidence that powder concentrations or clusters likely formed when creating these specimens. The luminous specimens had much more variance in ultimate strain than the non-luminous specimens, showing that the addition of luminous powder induced more variation to a GFRP's tensile properties. The GFRP's average elastic modulus increased as the luminous concentration in the matrix increased, as shown in Figure 5c. This means that a self-luminous GFRP became stiffer as higher concentrations of luminous

powder were placed in the matrix. Similar to the ultimate strain, the additional luminous powder caused the specimens to have more variable moduli.

(a) Avg. tensile strength vs. luminous powder

(b) Avg. ultimate strain vs. luminous powder

(c) Avg. elastic modulus vs. luminous powder

Figure 5: Tensile properties in control

MOISTURE EFFECTS

Test Procedure

To evaluate the effects of water on self-luminous GFRPs, 0% and 40% luminance specimens were submerged in ambient tap water, and their tensile and luminance properties were evaluated after 7, 28, 90, and 150 days of submersion. To determine the material's moisture content over time, the weight of each specimen was recorded when dry and after 5 hours, 20.5 hours, 29 hours, 7 days, 28 days, 90 days, 120 days, and 150 days of submersion.

Moisture Absorption

Within 29 hours of submersion, the GFRPs reached roughly 25% of their absorption capacity. As shown in Figure 6, the rate of absorption was highest at the onset of water, but this rate decreased the longer the GFRP was submerged. Beyond 90 days, the moisture curve began to flatten, significantly dampening the rate at which water was absorbed. The typical GFRPs displayed an absorption capacity of roughly 2.1%, while the self-luminous GFRPs had a lower absorption capacity of about 1.9%. Luminous powder has less water absorption capacity than that of epoxy, so self-luminous GFRPs have a lower absorption capacity compared to normal GFRPs.

Figure 6: Average moisture content over time

Water Effects on Luminance

Self-luminous GFRPs subjected to water followed the same logarithmic decay trend and duration as the dry condition, but experienced a slightly smaller initial luminance, as shown in Figure 7. Other than a slight decrease in initial brightness, water did not have a significant impact on a GFRP's luminance since the brightness curves align after about 3 minutes of light removal and the time of emittance is similar.

Figure 7: Luminance over time for submerged specimens

Water Effects on Tensile Properties

Unlike the control test, little to no cracking occurred while testing the submerged specimens. Roughly 26.7% of the 0% luminance specimens experienced Type I failure, 60% failed in type II, and 13.3% failed in type III. For the 40% luminance specimens, 12.5% failed in type I, 37.5% failed in type II, and 50% failed in type III. The longer the specimens were submerged, the more often they exhibited type I failure, showing that moisture caused GFRPs to have a brittle failure mode. Water degrades a GFRP's fiber to matrix interface and causes debonding after the material is exposed for prolonged periods (Bian et al., 2012; Wang et al., 2015a; Wang et al., 2015b; Al-Salloum et al., 2012). The brittle failure modes and absence of cracking during testing provide evidence that the water caused the fibers to debond from the matrix. After debonding occurred, the matrix was much more likely to fail across the fibers rather than shear through the matrix, like the control tests.

The average tensile strength, ultimate strain, and elastic modulus of the 0% and 40% luminance specimens over time submerged in water are shown in Figure 8. An error bar is also provided in the figure to show the range of data collected. As moisture content increased, the tensile strength of the self-luminous GFRPs decreased. The 0% luminance specimens had a slightly higher average strength after 7 and 28 days submerged but saw a significant decrease in strength after 90 and 150 days submerged. The study of Kim et al. (2006) confirms these results, as it found that GFRP composites submerged in 20 °C deionized water experienced a slight increase in tensile strength within 30 days of submersion but decreased after submerged for longer periods. After a prolonged period submerged, both the specimens saw a significant decrease in tensile strength. After 90 days submerged, the tensile strength of the 0% and 40% specimens decreased a total of 17.9% and 16.5%, respectively. After 150 days, the tensile strength remained similar as after 90 days of submersion. The moisture content only slightly increased after 90 days submerged, so without additional water absorbed, the tensile strength remained the same. This provided evidence that the GFRP's tensile strength was affected by its moisture content rather than the time submerged under water.

(a) Tensile strength vs. time submerged

(b) Ultimate strain vs. time submerged

(c) Elastic modulus vs. time submerged

Figure 8: Average tensile properties of submerged specimens

Furthermore, the ultimate strain decreased as the moisture content increased for both luminous and non-luminous GFRP specimens, shown in Figure 8b. Once the material neared its absorption capacity, the ultimate strain remained stagnant. Like its tensile strength, the ultimate strain was similar after 90 and 150 days submerged. The elastic modulus for each specimen type remained roughly equivalent regardless of submersion time, as shown in Figure 8c. The 40% luminance specimen had a slightly higher elastic modulus than the 0% specimens, but this was expected based on the results previously described. Overall, the self-luminous GFRP had similar results or fell in the range of the nonluminous GFRP, so it can be concluded that the addition of luminous powder does not affect how a GFRP reacts to water.

CONCLUSIONS

This study was aimed at evaluating the luminous characteristics and tensile properties of self-luminous glass fiber reinforced polymers with different amounts of luminous powder and exposed to moist environment. The following highlights the significant conclusions drawn from this study:

1. Upon removal of its light source, the afterglow performance of self-luminous GFRPs experience logarithmic decay over time.
2. The intensity of light and the length of emittance increases with additional luminous powder, but the rate of change decreases at higher powder concentrations. The maximum afterglow performance a GFRP can obtain is near 80% of the epoxy's weight in luminance powder.
3. Luminous powder has negligible effect on a GFRP's tensile strength and ultimate strain until luminous concentrations of 60% of the epoxy weight or higher. A GFRP's elastic modulus increases with luminous concentration.
4. Self-luminous GFRPs have a lower absorption capacity compared to normal GFRPs.
5. Moisture does not significantly impact a GFRP's afterglow performance.
6. As a GFRP's moisture content increases, the tensile strength and ultimate strain significantly decrease, but the elastic modulus remains unchanged. GFRP's mechanical properties are dependent on the material's moisture content rather than the amount of time exposed to water.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The first author was supported by the financial aid from Marquette University during his graduate studies. The glass fibers and epoxy were donated by Simpson Strong-Tie and Fyfe.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

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